

BEAGLE
BLUE OCEANS STRATEGY
FOR VALUE CREATION

D1.1 BEAGLE Kick-Off Meeting, Coordination, Management and Monitoring

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BEAGLE
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

These minutes summarize the main discussions of the BEAGLE kick-off meeting (KoM), which took place in a hybrid format (onsite and online) on January 30th and 31st at URV Bellissens in Reus, Tarragona province, Spain. Every partner was represented by at least one participant, except for NextMove, which could not attend due to scheduling conflicts of an important industry event. Discussions centred on objectives, strategies, and work package outlines, laying a collaborative foundation. Presentations and planning sessions emphasized operational and administrative cohesion. With a focus on immediate next steps, including detailed project planning and establishing communication channels, the meeting set a dynamic and positive course for the BEAGLE project's journey ahead.

<Kick-off Meeting>	
DATE	<30th-January 2024> - <13:00-17:15> Plus consortium dinner <31st-January 2024> - <9:00-13:00> Plus working lunch
PROJECT	BLUE OCEANS STRATEGY FOR VALUE CREATION - BEAGLE
PLACE	REUS, TARRAGONA PROVINCE, SPAIN

OBJECTIVES OF THE MEETING	<p>The primary goals of the KoM included:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Presenting an overview of the project, detailing specific objectives, tasks, expected outcomes, and deliverables. ▪ Outlining the consortium's workflow, including task allocation. ▪ Solving task overlaps to turn them into chances for teamwork. ▪ Deciding on forthcoming actions and steps. ▪ Finalizing and solidifying the work plan for the first year.
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This report provides a comprehensive overview of the essential discussions and decisions made during our meeting. It highlights the strategic decision points, organizational frameworks, and the allocation of tasks and responsibilities among the participants. The focal points of our dialogue were centred around establishing:

- The operational framework and methodologies for the BEAGLE project, ensuring efficient and high-quality completion of tasks.
- The decision to use Microsoft Teams' team functionality as our main repository tool ensures a centralized and accessible platform for project information, supported by a detailed Data Management and Quality Assurance Plan.

The meeting ended on a positive note, with partners reaffirming their dedication and ability to work together effectively. They agreed to focus on certain areas within the BEAGLE project through a collaborative and challenge-based approach with stakeholders. There was also strong interest in further shaping our approach and using our main collaboration tool to improve project management and teamwork.

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

BEAGLE	Blue Oceans Strategy for Value Creation
C	Call for Proposal
D	Deliverable
EU	European Union
KoM	Kick-off Meeting
T	Task
WP	Work-Package

1 INTRODUCTION

This report is structured into three primary sections: The initial section offers an introduction, providing the report's background and objectives; the second section details the meeting's minutes, organized according to the project's Work Packages (WP). This organization serves as a methodological approach to thoroughly examine the tasks, timelines, and other specifics of each unit of work. The final section presents a comprehensive work plan for the first year, visually illustrated with timelines, tasks, and expected deliverables. Additionally, this report includes specific sub-sections for each WP, highlighting key discussion points and agreements to streamline the coordination of planned activities. During the KoM, the consortium prioritized the clear articulation of each WP's goals, their interconnections, and consensus on future tasks and responsibilities.

The KoM took place in the Faculty of Business and Economics at the Universitat Rovira i Virgili (Reus, Spain) on January 30-31, 2024.

BACKGROUND AND AIM

In preparation for the BEAGLE project KoM, a series of preliminary steps were undertaken:

- A basic PPT template was created by the coordinator. This template was sent to each WP leader to assist them in preparing a presentation detailing their WP goals and the activities planned to achieve these goals. The presentations were to be finalized and submitted by January 30th.
- The preparatory actions included:
 1. Confirming with the coordinator the list of attendees from partner organization for the KoM.
 2. Confirming with each WP leader the preparation and coordination of WP-specific presentations. These presentations would be the responsibility of the WP leaders to organize and present.
- Prior to the KoM, several collaborative sessions were conducted amongst partners to ensure a unified approach across different WPs. These sessions aimed to:
 1. Pinpoint synergies
 2. Eliminate task duplication
 3. Define clear methodologies and the scope of each WP's tasks

During this phase, we observed proactive collaboration among partners, who made efforts to integrate their tasks into a unified plan.

The agenda for the KoM is as follows, with the proceedings held as per this agenda. The signature document of meeting participants is enclosed in Annex 1.

BEAGLE KoM AGENDA (1/2)

BEAGLE Kick-off Meeting on Jan 30-31 – Final agenda

January 30, 2024 13:00-17:15	KoM-1st Day-Venue: Sala Graus, Campus Bellissens, Faculty of Business and Economics. Universitat Rovira i Virgili. Av. de la Universitat, 1, 43204 Reus, Tarragona, Spain 13:00 - Offering of Stand-up, Casual Catered Lunch
13:30	Welcome & Round the table (partner presentation) – 40’ (5 minutes each partner organization)
14:10	Project overview-Framing the expected results – URV – Xiaoni Li – 30’
14:40	EU Project Officer Presentation – Roberta Monachello – 20’
15:00	WP1 - COORDINATION, MANAGEMENT AND MONITORING (URV) – Xiaoni Li – 20’ (10’ present + 10’ discussion) Presentation of the project overall Work Plan/ Project results/ Deliverable list -Data Management Plan -Financial and final report -Quality Assurance Plan, and guidelines for consortium operation (governing bodies, reviewing of deliverables and risk assessment) Debate & Joint agreement
15:20	WP2 - BEAGLE NETWORK GOVERNANCE (CTAG) – Raul Urbano Escobar – 40’ (20’ present + 20’ discussion) -Mapping knowledge valorisation network and thematic niches (CTAG). -MTs (Mixed Teams) committee operative report (CTAG). -A-I (academia-industry) knowledge creation marketplace (F6S). -Open call for recruitment of professionals (F6S). Debate & Joint agreement
16:00	Coffee break
16:30	WP3 - DISCOVER OPPORTUNITIES. Phase I (CTBG) – Rada Betovska & Veronika Arsova – 40’ (20’ present + 20’ discussion) -Methodology for inventory of opportunities –demand -Catalogue of innovation demand video-factsheets Debate & Joint agreement
17:15	Optional Cultural Visit Location: Gaudi Center, Plaça del Mercadal, 3, 43201 Reus.
20:30	Dinner at Museu del Vermut, Carrer de Vallroquetes, 7, 43201 Reus Website: https://www.museudelvermut.com

BEAGLE KoM AGENDA (2/2)

January 31, 2024 9:00-13:00	KoM-2nd Day-Venue: Sala Graus, Campus Bellissens, Faculty of Business and Economics. Universitat Rovira i Virgili. Av. de la Universitat, 1, 43204 Reus, Tarragona, Spain
9:15	WP4 - CO-CREATE KNOWLEDGE VALORISATION. Phase II (WBU) – Miroslav Špaček – 40' (20' present + 20' discussion) -Catalogue of innovation offer video-factsheets -Innovation matching report -Academia-industry valorisation Debate & Joint agreement
10:00	WP5 - CONSOLIDATE THE KNOWLEDGE VALORISATION OF ACADEMIA-INDUSTRY. Phase III (URV) – Xiaoni Li – 40' (20' present + 20' discussion) -Assessment on academia-industry collaborations (URV). -Report on consolidated collaborations: agreements (URV). -Report on Action Plans (CTAG). Debate & Joint agreement
10:40	Coffee break
11:10	WP6 - DISSEMINATION, REPLICATION, EXPLOITATION AND COMMUNICATION (F6S) – Daniela Fonseca & Ivana Ilic – 40' (20' present + 20' discussion) -PDER&COM plan report -Internal and External comm & engagement -Impact, replication, and maximization Debate & Joint agreement
12:00	Pending issues and decisions Wrap up and conclusions - 20'
13:00	Lunch at Vermuts Rofes, Carrer de Sant Vicenç, 21, 23, 43201 Reus. Website: www.vermutsrofes.com

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BEAGLE KoM ATTENDEES

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* For health reason, Pavlina Hejdukova could not attend presentially to the KoM.

NextMove was unable to attend the KoM due to a scheduling conflict of an important industry event. They had a follow-up meeting via Teams with the coordinator URV on 6th Feb 2024.

2 MEETING MINUTES

The venue of the meeting was in Campus Bellissens, located at Av. de la Universitat, 1, 43204 Reus, Tarragona province, Spain, where the Faculty of Business and Economics at the Universitat Rovira i Virgili is situated (please see the map below).

The meeting participants began arriving at the venue at 12:30, starting with a welcome catering lunch to greet everyone. After that, Ana Beatriz Hernandez, the Vice Dean of the Faculty of Business and Economics of URV, delivered a short welcome speech.

(Ana Beatriz Hernandez, Vice Dean of the Faculty of Business and Economics of URV)

Following the opening remarks, Xiaoni Li initiated the meeting with a 'round the table' segment, during which all attending partners introduced their respective organizations.

(Xiaoni Li, from URV)

(Domènec Savi Puig Valls, from URV)

(Michaela Krechovska, from UWB)

(Maher Asal, from HV)

(Daniela Filipa da Silva Fonseca, from F6S)

(Diego Rodriguez Nion, from CTAG)

(Ivan Souček, from SCHP)

(Katarzyna Kowalska, from UNIMOS)

(Rada Betovska, from CTBG)

After the introductions, Xiaoni Li, the project coordinator from URV, started the session with a presentation on the BEAGLE project. The presentation highlighted the goal of strengthening collaboration between universities and industries to boost innovation through strategic partnerships.

Project Objectives and Approach

The Challenge of Academia-Industry Collaboration

- **Main Objective:**
 - Enhance productivity and efficiency in **knowledge valorisation** and **value creation in A-I linkages**.
 - Implement **Blue Oceans Strategy** for innovative market creation in the Transfer of Knowledge market.
 - Focus on increasing collaboration across **different countries** and **distinctive sectors**.

- **Specific Objectives:**
 - **SO1:** Promote best practices exchange in knowledge valorisation to discover **new market niches**.
 - **SO2:** Foster **stronger A-I links and synergies** through co-creation in detection of demand opportunities (**Phase I**) and innovation offers (**Phase II**).
 - **SO3:** Consolidate knowledge valorisation (**Phase III**) in the form of action plan, preparing projects for **investment and support from European instruments**.

The presentation detailed the project's goals to foster public-private partnerships, improve the valorisation of research outcomes, and create new market opportunities through co-creation. Highlighting the project's approach to overcoming current challenges in R&I investment within the EU, the coordinator laid out a roadmap for achieving impactful cross-sectoral collaboration, setting a strong foundation for the project's implementation phase.

Innovation funnel and BEAGLE expected outcome

The BEAGLE project employs an innovative funnel approach to streamline academia-industry collaboration, starting with 120 open calls, encompassing both replies or demands from the industry sector and offers from academia. Through a rigorous selection process, these will be narrowed down to 60, further refined to 40, and ultimately, 20 action plans will be developed. This structured methodology ensures focused and impactful outcomes, promoting efficient knowledge exchange and co-creation between academia and industry to foster novel market innovations.

Subsequently, EU officer Roberta Monachello from the European Research Executive Agency delivered a presentation on the BEAGLE project, focusing on crucial aspects such as the importance of monitoring and reporting, cross-cutting issues, and the availability of extra resources. The presentation highlighted the need for both technical and financial reporting, the process of audits and amendments, and detailed the involvement of the European Research Executive Agency in advancing research and innovation. Key takeaways included the emphasis on continuous and periodic reporting, adherence to cost eligibility rules, and the critical role of impact, communication, dissemination, and ethics in the project's execution.

EU officer Roberta Monachello

Main points of discussion

Maher Asal from HV inquired about publication requirements, specifically if there were any ranking necessities for publications. Roberta Monachello clarified that there are no specific ranking requirements. Xiaoni Li contributed to the conversation by mentioning the importance of publishing in indexed journals. Following the discussion, Roberta Monachello had to leave the session but expressed her hope to join the following morning's presentations. The rest of the European Commission members remained in the online meeting room for further discussions.

WP1 | COORDINATION, MANAGEMENT AND MONITORING

Agenda point 1 - Responsible partner (**URV** Xiaoni Li, Domènec Puig, Xavier Càmara, Daniel Ferrer, M. Teresa Sorrosal, M. Del Carmen Molina, M. Dels Àngels Amenós, Hatem A. Rashwan and Yin Shi)

(Xiaoni Li from URV introducing WP1)

Summary of the discussion

Xiaoni Li highlighted WP1's goals and tasks, stressing its critical role in aligning all WPs for unified project advancement. To foster effective project management, Teams was chosen as the main communication platform, establishing dedicated areas for each WP to enhance partner collaboration and information exchange. This setup is designed to ensure project clarity and streamline progress monitoring. The project timeline and updates will be easily accessible through the Teams group, allowing partners to keep track of deadlines, action progress, and task completion efficiently.

Main objectives of the WP1

- Define an effective strategic and day-to-day coordination to ensure the achievement of BEAGLE objectives on time and within the allocated budget
- Assure proper interaction between partners and external stakeholders
- Establish effective communication and reporting channels with European Commission
- Identify early conflicts, mitigate risks and apply corrective measures
- Ensure proper quality management to guarantee timely delivery of high-quality final results.

Financial Record-Keeping and Legal Compliance for EC Project Obligations

- We have a contractual obligation towards the EC to keep financial records for the project, and this includes reporting of actual costs or resources.

And

1. Comply with record keeping and other legal obligations.
2. Keep documentation to demonstrate that the activities in Annex 1 have been carried out, and by whom. This is the same technical documentation as for all grants.
3. Also, for clustering activities, keep documentation as required by good research practices such as minutes, technical documents, guidelines, proceedings in conferences, and publications.

Timeline proposal for WP1

Main points of discussion

There were two main points for discussion:

1. Xiaoni Li outlined the project's management strategies, focusing on legal and financial aspects, and clarified budget management.
2. Ivan Souček inquired whether there is a need to prepare a template for funding, deliverables, etc. Xiaoni Li answered that the upcoming presentation by F6S will provide the necessary information, as they are tasked with creating a standardized format template for significant reports and deliverables. It was also mentioned that a repository system would be established through Microsoft Teams for the project's management. Daniela Filipa da Silva Fonseca will introduce a website and communication PPT template, focusing on visual funding from the EC and instructions for use.

Action Points:

Deadline	Action
Feb 29 th , 2024	D.1.1. Preparation of KoM minutes by project coordinator. This will be shared with partners who will have one week to check, complete, suggest or modify before the deadline for submission
Feb 15 th , 2024	Draft procedures for deliverables to be circulated and agreed upon by partners

WP2 | BEAGLE NETWORK GOVERNANCE

Agenda point 2 – Responsible partners (**CTAG** Raul Urbano Escobar, Diego Rodriguez Nion/ **F6S** Daniela Filipa da Silva Fonseca, Ivana Ilic)

(Raul Urbano from CTAG and Daniela Filipa da Silva Fonseca from F6S introducing WP2)

Summary of the discussion

The WP2 BEAGLE NETWORK GOVERNANCE, presented by Raul Urbano Escobar, highlights that the BEAGLE network aims to foster knowledge valorisation and academia-industry collaboration to create new market niches. This involves selecting top thematic niches to be addressed using the BEAGLE methodology in WPs 3, 4, and 5. Partners contribute expertise to a database that will inform the establishment of a BEAGLE marketplace, with F6S hosting a dedicated community page for synergy and real-time interaction. An open call will recruit participants to explore these niches, followed by a multi-stage evaluation process. This initiative is presented by Raul Urbano, focusing on CTAG, and Daniela Filipa da Silva Fonseca, who covers the F6S aspects.

Main objectives

- (1) **Mapping** best practices on knowledge valorisation.
- (2) Analysing pain points and opportunities of **new market niches**.
- (3) Setting up the governance model of the network throughout **Mixed Teams (MTs)** devoted to lead thematic niches.
- (4) Deployment of the **marketplace** based on video-factsheets on innovation demand and offer.
- (5) Launching **recruitment process (OC)** for industry and academia.

Task 2.1 Mapping best practices on knowledge valorisation networks

The aim of this task is to set up the scene of the BEAGLE network to foster the exchange of experience in knowledge valorisation and collaborations between Academia and Industry stakeholders when creating new market niches (Blue Oceans Strategy). As part of the analysis, it is conducted the **identification of international collaborations** as well as the identification of **methodologies, programmes and initiatives** that **partners of the project conduct** on knowledge valorisation. These will be targeting practices to be improved after the introduction of BEAGLE methodology, **and it will be analysed during Task 5.1**.

Task 2.2 Mapping of thematic niches

This task aims to understand the main pain points and opportunities of (at least) 40 new market niches to select top#12 thematic niches the project will address within the innovation funnel as planned in WP3-WP4 and WP5. To do so, each partner contributes to the elaborate of a database of new horizons of opportunities and particular businesses based on their well-known of sector, profile, background expertise and innovation prospects of its companies' members or researchers. Several interactions take place to discuss and agree on the 12 main thematic niches on which the experiment will focus. The output from this task (12 thematic fields) is considered in Task 2.3.

Task 2.3 Appointment of the Mixed Teams and monitoring of the actions (MT).

- Each MT address one specific thematic niche.
- Each partner designates a delegate(s) (or representative(s)) to join one or several MTs.
- Delegates might be innovation advisors (or similar profile) capable to reach and engage professionals from their respective entity to ensure:
 - o Phase I. (WP3) Engage to apply to Open call for industry or demand (depend on its affiliation).
 - o Phase II. (WP4) Support their professionals (from university or companies) during co-creation activities including video factsheets creation
 - o Phase III. (WP5) Support their professionals to initiate the formalization of collaboration.
- The team of each MT must comply with gender and dimension balance
- Each MT designate a chair who will report directly to task leader (for internal communications) as well as the public point of contact (for external communications).
- The MTs oversee inventorying demand-side of the industry (WP3) and offer-side of the academia (WP4), in collaboration with WPLEaders.
- Once set-up, the committee formed by the MTs will meet regular one in-person during a project meeting and one online, to ensure quality assurance of outputs from WP3 and WP4. The committee will update D2.3 on M20 and M30.
- The MTs model set up the governance model for replicability as well as exploitation plan foreseen in WP6.

Task 2.4 Deploy academia-industry knowledge valorisation marketplace

The aim of this task is to establish the marketplace of the BEAGLE network. All partners contribute with definition of requirements and expectations. Requirements on profiles are defined by Task 2.2 and should enable the different interactions for facilitation connections between academia-industry participants as planned within WP3-WP4-WP5. The F6S platform will have a dedicated BEAGLE community page which will be available on the BEAGLE website and also which will power the marketplace providing a solid launchpad from which users can matchmake and identify synergies. This F6S BEAGLE community page will be linked via an API to the BEAGLE platform in order to maintain its brand identity and allow opportunities for continuous growth post project. This will allow stakeholders to interact with each other in real time.

Task 2.5 Open call for recruitment of professionals

The aim of this task is to launch an open call (OC) for recruitment of participants to discover new market niches (output from Task 2.2) lead by each MTs (Task 2.3). A call text including guide for applicants as well as an AP-application form will be published during at least 2 months to ensure a good quality and quantity of applicants. The MTs will oversee evaluation process –which might include interviews. The OC will have several cut-offs (with thematic differentiation) to facilitate MTs on conducting on WP3 (in particular Task 3.1) and WP4 (in particular Task 4.1). Therefore D2.5 will have a 1st release for the OC for inventory of value proposition (linkage with Task 3.1) and a 2nd release for the OC for creation innovation proposal (linkage with Task 4.1). The D2.6 is a report with results and conclusions from the OC process. The preparation includes the setup of all required Open call documents: OC text, guidelines, materials, contract templates, proposal templates, communication key messages and programme value proposition via www.f6s.com. As well, the evaluation of results will have different stages: 1) compilation of data like statistics from the preproposals, submissions and incidences during the open calls and during the execution of the projects; 2) analysis of data to visualise things like country coverage, categorisation of applicants, successful rate of events, percentage of successful companies, types of non-eligibility, etc. 3) improvement lines definition like reinforcing the open calls in a certain part of Europe, being more accurate in the definition of certain rules, etc.

Main points of discussion

1. Task 2.2's progress on identifying new market niches was addressed, with an emphasis on the lack of current examples and a proposed future discussion to explore these niches further.
2. The conversation highlighted the challenges of motivating companies of the industry to participate actively in the open call, with Ivan Souček noting the difficulty compared to academia, and Raul Urbano suggesting protective measures to ensure motivation and participation.
3. Ivan Souček inquired about the meaning of "recruitment" within the context of the project. Raul Urbano clarified that this open call will not need any financial support of a third party to hold the 240 open calls. The input is from volunteers of the industry and academia and the open call will be linked to the F6S platform.

Action Points:

Deadline	Action
Jun 30 th , 2024	Task 2.1. Conduct mapping of best practices on knowledge valorisation networks.
Sep 30 th , 2024	Task 2.2. Map at least 40 new market niches to select the top 12 for thematic focus.
Jun 30 th , 2025	Task 2.3. Appoint Mixed Teams (MTs) and monitor actions for leading knowledge valorisation in thematic niches.
Jun 30 th , 2024	Task 2.4. Deploy the academia-industry knowledge valorisation marketplace through the F6S platform.
Dec 31 st , 2025	Task 2.5. Open call for recruitment of professionals to discover new market niches.

WP3 | DISCOVER OPPORTUNITIES. Phase I

Agenda point 3 - Responsible partners (CTBG Rada Betovska, Veronika Arsova)

(Rada Betovska from CTBG introducing WP3)

Summary of the discussion

Rada Betovska, from CTBG, outlined the WP3 objectives and how they interlink with other WPs, presenting a comprehensive schedule and task description:

1. Implementing co-creation activities to generate a comprehensive database of opportunities and demand video-factsheets.
2. Engaging Mixed Teams (MTs) for the development and validation of system innovation canvases.
3. Scheduling activities to ensure the effective recording and utilization of innovation demand insights.

Main objectives:

- **Help MTs select the best opportunities on demand side from the industry** in their respective market niche.
- **Conduct co-creation activities for makers to create a database of opportunities** (video-factsheets, workshops, survey, interviews, system innovation approaches).
- **Record 60 demand video-factsheets.**

Main Tasks – WP3 – Task 3.1

Task 3.1 - Inventory of Value Creation Opportunities

- Development of **system innovation canvas for mapping the business/market innovation expectations and opportunities** of the professionals from the four participating industry clusters: specific assessment for each target sector to survey business/market innovation expectation and opportunities.
- **Training for MTs on the methodology** for mapping of expectations and opportunities.
- **Challenged workshops:** validate innovation expectation and value creation opportunities through the use of the designed system innovation tool.

Main Tasks – WP3 – Task 3.2

Task 3.2 Creation of Innovation Demand video-factsheets:

- **Creation of mixed innovation assessment teams**, each participating **industry cluster manager** will team up with each participating **R&I entity technology advisor** and **innovation advisor**. These advisors will be previously **appointed by the R&I entities** and will last the whole BEAGLE project duration.
- Review and validate the database of opportunities (output from Task 3.1) to **record the Innovation Demand video-factsheets to be transferred to R&I entities'** different researchers;
- **Creation of innovation demand video-factsheets**, upload on the virtual platform and viewing sessions with the chosen researchers by the mixed teams.

Timeline proposal for WP3

Main points of discussion

The main points of discussion surrounding Ivan Souček 's question about the content of the video-factsheet are:

1. Clarification on the specific information and insights to be included in the video-factsheets, detailing innovation opportunities and proposals from the industry's demand side. Innovation expectation should be reflected in video factsheets.
2. Discussion on how these video-factsheets will serve to engage stakeholders and promote collaboration within the BEAGLE project, emphasizing their role in visualizing potential for innovation.

Action Points:

Deadline	Action
Apr 30 th , 2025	Task 3.1. Conduct co-creation activities to discover industry demand-side opportunities, develop system innovation canvas, and record conclusions in the database of opportunities.
Aug 31 st , 2025	Task 3.2. Create mixed innovation assessment teams, review and validate the opportunities database, record and upload innovation demand video-factsheets, and organize viewing sessions with researchers.

WP4 | CO-CREATE KNOWLEDGE VALORISATION. Phase II

Agenda point 4 - Responsible partners (**UWB** - Miroslav Spacek, Michaela Krechovska, Petra Tausl Prochazkova)

(Miroslav Spacek from UWB introducing WP4)

Summary of the discussion

Miroslav Spacek discussed the objectives for this WP, focusing on:

1. The creation and dissemination of innovation proposal video-factsheets, aiming to map out market niches and innovation opportunities.
2. Facilitating innovation matching to connect these opportunities with industry needs.
3. Enhancing academia-industry valorisation through strategic collaboration and knowledge sharing.

WP4 is designed to interlink with WP2 and WP3, enhancing the overall project's impact by leveraging shared insights and fostering a collaborative environment for stakeholders. This WP will contribute significantly to the development of the project's innovative framework, with a particular focus on creating a dynamic marketplace for knowledge exchange.

Task 4.1 Creation of innovation Proposal video-factsheets (May 2025 - December 2025)

Participants: URV, HV, F6S, CTAG

- **Knowledge valorisation surveys (output from Task 2.5), specific assessment of market niches.**
- **Activities:** Output Task 2.5 analysis, resources search for up-to-date information, market demand assessment? market niches proposal, discussion with participants on training webinars, choice of respondents
- **Develop innovative offer for opportunities detected.**
- **Activities :** Innovation opportunities identification, Completion of the List of Opportunities Innovation steps usable for detected opportunities, training webinars with participants
- **Creation of innovation proposals, video fact-sheets, upload on the virtual platform.**
- **Activities :** Concept of innovation proposal structure, processing each opportunity to innovation proposal, methodology of video fact-sheets creation (manual), piloting the sample of video-fact sheets, establishing of the Catalogue of innovation offer video-factsheets. Participants' Feedback evaluation.

Deliverables

D4.1: Catalogue of innovation offer video-factsheets (December 2025)

Funded by the European Union

BEAGLE

Task 4.2 Innovation matching (August 2025 - April 2026)

Participants: URV, HV, CTAG

- **The committee of MTs will oversee carrying out a human intelligence assessment of both, demand and offer sectoral video-factsheets in each mixed teams of R&I entities advisors and the cluster managers.**
- **Activities:** multi-criteria assessment of video fact-sheets, feasibility assessment, workshops organization, on-line meetings, Innovation matching report.
- **Proposing of viewing of the Innovation Offer video-factsheets to the industry agents (CTOs).**
- **Activities:** Presentations on workshops, uploading video-fact sheets to virtual video platform, workshop with industry agents, validation of video-factsheets, updating video-factsheets.

Deliverables

D4.2: Innovation matching report (April 2026)

BEAGLE

Task 4.3 Academia-industry valorisation (January 2026 - June 2026)

Participants: URV, HV, CTAG, NEXTMOVE, CTBG, SCHP, UNIMOS

- **The portfolio generating and publishing in the virtual platform serving as inspiration and best practices for creating new niches.**
- **Activities:** Possible shortlisting video-factsheets (if needed), virtual platform improvement, marketing support of video-fact sheets dissemination
- **Potential disruptive innovation factors selection.**
- **Activities :** identification of signalling effect of disruptive innovation, assessment of potential of disruptive innovation factors, publication outputs
- **Outline of instruments supporting the European cohesion policy or the Recovery and Resilience Facility.**
- **Activities :** performance analysis, synergic effects identification, manuals for innovation identification and implementation, strategic framework for the treatment of innovation opportunities, market traction strategy, publication outputs.

Deliverables

D4.3: Academia – industry portfolio published (June 2026)

BEAGLE

Methodology used in WP4

- **Content analysis** – extraction of relevant information from available documents (Annual reports, scientific databases search-WoS, Scopus, ProQuest, commercial databases – Reuters, scientific and professional literature).
- **Social network analysis** – collection of information from accessible networks (LinkedIn, Cefic, company websites)
- **Contextual interviews** – semi-structured interviews with company managers, experts, innovators, opinion makers, academicians
- **Questionnaire survey** – questionnaires distributed to cluster members (Czech chemical companies)
- **Creative methods** – WQIS, Delphi, Mind maps, Brainstorming, Disney strategy, Synectics, What if? 5Why s? etc.
- **Expert method** – collecting expert’s opinions of specific problem or its solution
- **Various analytical methods:** multi-criteria assessment of innovation opportunities, feasibility assessment
- **Statistical methods** – with regard to papers publishing
- **AI application:** - ChatGPT

Main points of discussion

1. Maher Asal raises concerns about the reliability and subjective quality of survey results, suggesting a need for critical evaluation of data used in research, highlighting the challenge of accessing valuable company-specific data which is not openly available but crucial for analysis.
2. Xiaoni Li further emphasises that at the core of this project is a co-creation experiment applying the blue ocean strategy to promote mechanisms that enhance R-I (Research-Industry) collaboration and action plans. This includes employing both qualitative and quantitative data to effectively address innovation issues, alongside the KPI for academic members to publish at least six papers in high-quality, indexed journals, without the necessity for specific impact factors.

Action Points:

Deadline	Action
Dec 31 st , 2025	Task 4.1. Conduct co-creation activities, knowledge valorisation surveys, develop innovative offers, and create/upload video-factsheets.
Apr 30 th , 2026	Task 4.2. Perform human intelligence assessment of demand and offer, propose viewing to industry agents.
Jun 30 th , 2026	Task 4.3. Generate and publish a portfolio on the virtual platform showcasing best practices for niche creation.

WP5 | CONSOLIDATE THE KNOWLEDGE VALORISATION OF ACADEMIA-INDUSTRY. Phase III

Agenda point 5 - Responsible partner (URV Xiaoni Li, Domènec Puig, Xavier Càmara, Daniel Ferrer, M. Teresa Sorrosal, M. Del Carmen Molina, M. Dels Àngels Amenós, Hatem A. Rashwan and Yin Shi)

(Xiaoni Li from URV introducing WP5)

Summary of the discussion

The main aims of this WP are explained:

1. Enhancing partnerships between academia and industry.
2. Utilizing BEAGLE methodologies for better research outcomes.
3. Drafting detailed plans for project implementation and funding approaches.

Main objectives of the WP5

This WP aims to determine activities to assist the MTs to conduct the Phase III of the methodology based on:

- (1) To facilitate the creation of connections based on the portfolio of A-I valorisation (outcome WP4)
- (2) To assess on the adequate formula to initiate R&I actions
- (3) To build-up a roadmap of each A-I connection (Action Plan)

Main tasks of the WP5 – Task 5.1

Task 5.1 Fostering academia-industry connections.

Leader URV, Participants, WBU, HV, CTAG, NEXTMOVE, CTBG, SCHP, UNIMOS. M25-M33

The aim of this task is to facilitate the creation of connections between R&I institutions and companies. To do so, the advisors and researchers from one side, and the industry agents and their cluster managers from the other side will facilitate the organization of bilateral meetings always performed from the demand side request.

Additionally, partners involved should assess how BEAGLE methodology is introduced or how BEAGLE contributes to encourage practices on R&I knowledge valorisation. Therefore, D5.1 includes a deeper analysis on the improvement done by the partners which was introduced in Task 2.1. (Deliverable D2.1).

Main tasks of the WP5 – Task 5.2

Task 5.2 Agreements on R&I actions.

Leader URV, Participants URV, WBU, HV, CTAG, NEXTMOVE, CTBG, SCHP, UNIMOS. M30-M35

The goal of this task is to assess and assist teams on determining the adequate formula of the agreement on R&I actions ensuring interest from both sides. The different formulas might be (but not limited to) transfer agreement, collaboration agreements or freedom-to-operate agreements. Support teams on formalising MoU and/or NDA agreements to initiate robust and confident collaborations.

Main tasks of the WP5 – Task 5.3

Task 5.3 Build-up individual value creation Action Plans

Leader CTAG, Participants URV, WBU, HV, CTAG, NEXTMOVE, CTBG, SCHP, UNIMOS. M30-M36

The aim of this task is to support teams on drafting individual Action Plans based on results from Task 5.2 for each of the connections initiated (outcome from Task 5.1). The scope of each Action Plans shall cover the roadmap to formalize the adequate formula of R&I Action as well as project conceptualisation, design, and preparation of proposals for funding programmes from the European cohesion policy or the Recovery and Resilience Facility as well as other EU instruments.

Link within innovation approach

Main points of discussion

Xiaoni Li proposed whether Teams could be used for internal communication and if there were any partners who might not know how to use it or have any issues. The entire group confirmed that using Teams for internal communication was feasible.

Action Points:

Deadline	Action
Sep 30 th , 2026	Task 5.1. URV to conduct and complete an assessment of academia-industry collaborations.
Nov 30 th , 2026	Task 5.2. URV to prepare a report on the consolidated collaborations and formal agreements achieved.
Nov 30 th , 2026	Task 5.3. CTAG to draft and finalize the report on individual Action Plans following the outcomes of Task 5.2.

WP6 | DISSEMINATION, REPLICATION, EXPLOITATION AND COMMUNICATION

Agenda point 6 - Responsible partners (**F6S** Daniela Filipa da Silva Fonseca, Ivana Ilic)

(Daniela Filipa da Silva Fonseca and Ivana Ilic from F6S introducing WP6)

Summary of the discussion

1. The proposal includes options for monthly, bi-monthly, or bi-weekly meetings to maintain regular coordination and communication.
2. The decision on the project's logo was made through a voting process.

Daniela Filipa da Silva Fonseca and Ivana Ilic presented the elements that were taken into consideration to develop the logo and approved it.

Main points of discussion

1. Hatem Rashwan asked how to innovate with existing tech in new sectors. Xiaoni Li suggested repurposing technology, like adapting dehydration sensors for athletes to automotive safety, aiming at unexplored markets. Raul Urbano emphasized using technology to meet new customer needs, especially in sustainability, to discover untapped niches without direct competition.
2. Xiaoni Li also advised each partner to assign a finance expert for handling financial aspects, ensuring smooth project management.

Action Points:

Deadline	Action
Jun 30 th . 2024	Task 6.1. F6S will develop a comprehensive communication and dissemination strategy, including a detailed map of target audiences and key messages.
Dec 31 st , 2026	D.6.2. F6S will compile a report on the implementation and effectiveness of the PDER&COM plan.
Feb 29 th , 2024	Task 6.2. F6S will execute strategies to foster engagement within the partnership, targeting key internal stakeholders.
Jun 30 th . 2024	Task 6.3. F6S will initiate activities aimed at engaging external stakeholders and establishing collaborations with relevant initiatives.

3 CONSOLIDATED 1st YEAR WORK PLAN

Work plan
January 1st 2024 - December 31st 2024

4 ANNEX 1: SIGNED LIST OF ATTENDEES

BEAGLE Kick-off Meeting

Attendance Tuesday 30th January 2024

Time: 13:00-17:15

Location: Faculty of Business and Economics, Sala Graus
Campus Bellissens, Universitat Rovira i Virgili, Av. de la Universitat, 4, 43204
Reus, Tarragona, Spain

Representative	Institution	Signature
Michaela Krechovska	WBU	
Pavlina Hejdukova	WBU	
Petra Tausl Prochazkova	WBU	
Miroslav Spacek	WBU	
Maher Asal	HV	
Daniela Filipa da Silva Fonseca	F6S	
Ivana Ilic	F6S	
Raul Urbano Escobar	CTAG	
Diego Rodríguez Nion	CTAG	
Ivan Souček	SCHP	
Ivo Stanček	SCHP	
Katarzyna Kowalska	UNIMOS	
Julia Kosikowska	UNIMOS	
Rada Betovska	CTBG	
Veronika Arsova	CTBG	
Domènec Savi Puig Valls	URV	

Hatem Rashwan	URV	
Xiaoni Li	URV	
Xavier Càmara Turull	URV	
Daniel Ferrer Guallar	URV	
Maria Dels Àngels Amenós Pardiñas	URV	
Maria Teresa Sorrosal Forradellas	URV	
María Del Carmen Molina Cobo	URV	
Yin Shi	URV	

BEAGLE Kick-off Meeting

Attendance Wednesday 31st January 2024

Time: 9:00-13:00

Location: Faculty of Business and Economics, Sala Graus
Campus Bellissens, Universitat Rovira i Virgili, Av. de la Universitat, 4, 43204
Reus, Tarragona, Spain

Representative	Institution	Signature
Michaela Krechovska	WBU	<i>Krechovska</i>
Pavlina Hejdukova	WBU	<i>Hejdukova</i>
Petra Tausl Prochazkova	WBU	<i>Tausl</i>
Miroslav Spacek	WBU	<i>Spacek</i>
Maher Asal	HV	<i>Asal</i>
Daniela Filipa da Silva Fonseca	F6S	<i>Daniela Fonseca</i>
Ivana Ilic	F6S	<i>I. Ilic</i>
Raul Urbano Escobar	CTAG	<i>R. Escobar</i>
Diego Rodríguez Nion	CTAG	<i>Diego Nion</i>
Ivan Souček	SCHP	<i>I. Souček</i>
Ivo Stanček	SCHP	<i>I. Stanček</i>
Katarzyna Kowalska	UNIMOS	<i>K. Kowalska</i>
JULIA KOSIKOWSKA Anna Bialik	UNIMOS	<i>Kordec</i>
Rada Betovska	CTBG	<i>R. Betovska</i>
Veronika Arsova	CTBG	<i>V. Arsova</i>

Domènec Savi Puig Valls	URV	
Hatem Rashwan	URV	
Xiaoni Li	URV	
Xavier Càmara Turull	URV	
Daniel Ferrer Guallar	URV	
Maria Dels Àngels Amenós Pardiñas	URV	
Maria Teresa Sorrosal Forradellas	URV	
María Del Carmen Molina Cobo	URV	
Yin Shi	URV	